

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Importance of Forensic Intelligence in Criminal Investigation Process and Solutions to Crimes

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Abstract

Forensic Intelligence is still a relatively new in the field of Forensic Science discipline. Its advancement in the criminal investigation process requires innovative techniques, methods, and strategies to combat local, regional, national international crimes, therefore, the services of Criminologists and Forensic Scientists are highly required in exploring new developments and directions for the modern policing system owing to technological advancement. This paper provides an in-depth study to help Academia and professionals in crime mitigation process in rural and urban communities to establish a holistic understanding to enhance realistic decisions that advance the frontiers of forensic science through intelligence investigation. First, this paper offers a scientific study and differentiation on the relevant definitions, such as Intelligence, Forensics, Forensic Intelligence, and local policing. Second, the research methodology depicted here was the qualitative method. Third, the study presents the importance of the application of forensic intelligence and its results in the criminal investigation process. Fourth, it reveals important discussions on the results obtained to solve the proposed problem ravaging some local communities. Forensic intelligence remains an artifact of a pragmatic policing culture that only institutes new practices based on demonstrable, research and practice-based effectiveness. Therefore, the researcher seeks to draw attention to efforts in the scholarly community to accumulate a body of evidence on the efficacy of forensic intelligence and in doing so, draws attention to the challenges remaining for scholars and professionals to further understand and advance the use of forensic intelligence in mainstream local policing.

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1. Introduction

The advancing role of intelligence has received a number of augmentations in support of its utility in the creation of crime analysis. In this context, intelligence is viewed as the combination of information

and the evaluation process. Intelligence Analysis is the processing of information or intelligence in a manner that is used for the resolving or separating of a thing into its parts, ascertainment of those parts, the tracing of things to their source to discover the general principles behind them, and a table or statement of the results of this process (Ribaux, et al 2019). Intelligence is a process that converts knowledge in raw form (information) into information that is capable of being understood, with added value, and information that has been evaluated in the context of its source and reliability (intelligence = Information + Evaluation).

Therefore, Forensic intelligence is the accurate, timely, and useful product of logically analyzing case-study data for investigation and intelligence purposes. Spaulding (2022) opined that the process of forensic intelligence connects several parallel strategic processes that can be align to the scientific method of analysis. Bell (2006) highlighted that forensic intelligence is viewed in two separate regards, which were relating to the delivery of Intelligence in Forensic casework, inherently produced as an Intelligence product useful for Police Investigation; and considering performance within forensic casework, also known as business Intelligence processes.

However, Forensic Intelligence production has been confined to discipline-specific activity, meaning that it is not typically integrated with other interpretations of evidence in a larger case assessment process; however, intelligence production can be completed to yield a priori information for other investigations and extend to drawing links with other unsolved cases. Lopez, et al (2020) described Forensic Intelligence as an aspect of the crime inquiry cycle that involves gathering and studying thoroughly useful case data across all cases to detect, prevent, investigate, and prosecute crime, especially in cases of serial and violent crime. These authors went ahead to state that incorporating forensic data into crime analysis can also help identify links, patterns, and trends, or correlate other information pertinent to the criminal activity; resulting actionable intelligence can then be used to disrupt and prevent crime, particularly serial and violent crime.

Therefore, the current state of affairs in Nigeria has caught the serious attention of professionals, researchers, and scholars, especially those in the criminology discipline, to seek for means of integrating forensic intelligence into the investigation process. The series of crimes that are on a rampage and ravaging the socio-economic development of this nation has prompted scholars to draw a distinctive view about crime. Lopez et al (2020) defined crime as acts or omissions forbidden by law that can be punished by imprisonment or fine. It is an act or omission that affects the community or a state and makes the offender criminally liable to punishment, either imprisonment, fine, or caution and discharge (Mennell & Shaw, 2016). However, both scholars and professionals viewed crime as an act of offence, which violates the law of the state and is strongly disapproved by society; thus, crime is termed to be a public wrong. Crimes such as murder, robbery, burglary, rape, drunken driving, child neglect, kidnapping, tax avoidance, bribery, corruption, etc., are common in developing countries and can be mitigated with forensic intelligence (Milne, 2019).

Meanwhile, the modern forensic intelligence is said to have introduced light to challenges encountered in using the traditional forensic science laboratory that involve rigorous procedures in detecting accurate result during criminal investigation process. This traditional forensic science laboratory process poses pressure to the conventional crime fighting system on ground because it only makes use of reasoning rather than allowing the application of scientific process which is an aspect of the modern forensic intelligence (Ribaux & Margot, 2013). This is particularly purpose made the application of forensic intelligence exceptional in most criminal cases, especially for systems that dedicated enough training time and knowledge to gain more insight during investigation process (Ross, 2020).

The modern criminal investigation process has called for independence, better normalize and control procedures that can provide high quality and unbiased or impartial services that should focus on best endpoint result to make criminal cases appearing in the Court of Law to have the best conclusions (Julian, et al 2017).

However, Ribaux et al (2019) stated that such criminal investigation procedure should be error free while still maintaining its crime detective assurance to provide excellent feedback to most high-profile cases or it may inevitably cause reduce expectation of the public. The sustainability of such procedure through reinforcement consistently will prevent errors and detect criminals easily during investigation process yielding unbiased outcomes will bring about justice and ultimately, correct a lot inefficiencies in the policing and security system (Legrand & Vogel, 2018).

Actually, and based on the above premises, it can be stated that those developed countries who have regards for investigation will also improve their policing system with forensic intelligent procedures and has brought in changes with an emergence of a more proactive style of policing, as well as a broad variety of new ways of tracing crimes. This kind of improvement dramatically promotes forensic science discipline including how it is perceived and what is expected from it. There is a persuasive incentive to make an effort to better express how forensic science relates to policing through forensic intelligence. It is based on this relationship of forensic science and policing that this study tends to evaluate how forensic intelligence can assist in curbing crimes in the policing system. Thus, the main aim of this paper is to examine the importance of Forensic Intelligence in criminal investigation process. Other objectives aimed to achieved are: To determine the level of exposure of law enforcement agency towards the concept of Forensic Intelligence. To determine whether there is existing computerized data of crimes committed within the local policing systems in the country. To determine how Forensic Science can be integrated with existing Intelligence system in curbing the crime rate. And finally, to ascertain level of significance of Forensic Intelligence in criminal Investigation process in the local policing system as evidence to show why the law enforcement agency should embrace the concept and practice of Forensic Intelligence in their practices.

2. Literature Review

2.1. *Forensic Intelligence and Local Policing*

Forensic intelligence is a kind of intelligence which is produced in the process of analysis of evidences through the use of existing data bases. Catalkaya and Karaman (2015) opined that Forensic intelligence is reaching to basic data such as suspect, crime scene or offensive weapon which is necessary for criminal judicial system by analyzing and comparing available data which may be collected before or after crime with available database such as criminal record, social media, and fingerprint archive by using scientific techniques.

Evidences found in scene of crime are important resource of information to solve out the criminal case if a successful criminalist study is carried out. Forensic intelligence takes criminal study a step further and it is the usage of information gathered from crime scene in analysis studies (Milne, 2012: p. 5). Intelligence which is related to a crime can be gathered before the occurrence of crime, during the crime or after the crime. From scholarly perspective, it is known that before the crime occurrence, if a policing system is designed to take measures after something happened, such measures can be considered as a reactive policing, an example of this king of policing is trying to catch or discover

criminals or culprits after crimes are committed, or after something has happened, or after someone has been murdered. But investigations are made to be carried out in a more proactive manners to even try to prevent the occurrence of crime. Gathering information before the occurrence of crime represents the preventive policing.

2.2. Forensic Science and Intelligence

Forensic science is often seen as an applied science used in criminal investigations and criminal trials. However, as discussed earlier, forensic science can play a vital role beyond criminal trials. Therefore, scholars in this aspect of study have the conceptual model for effectiveness of forensic science research or project leads to forensic intelligence. A conceptual model for the effectiveness of the forensic science project, adapted from Julian et al (2017). All these models were adopted to bring out the picture of what Forensic Intelligence is and how it can be applied or has been applied by researchers. This is because an in-depth knowledge and understanding are required before this concept can be truly used in crime investigation by the law enforcement agencies.

3. Research Methodology

This study adopted both qualitative and quantitative research procedures to establish a fact seeking findings. Primary data used were generated through the use of a case study research design. The sample size of this study was respondents who were members of the Nigerian Police Force across Lagos state, Senior Lecturers and Master’s Degree Students in the Criminology discipline.

Table 1. The Sample Size Distribution.

Participants’ Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Senior Lecturers	41	19.81%
Postgraduate Scholars	65	31.40%
Police Headquarters, Ikeja	37	17.87%
Force C/D Headquarters, Alagbon	64	30.92%
Total	207	100.0%

4. Presentation of Results and Findings

5. Analysis of Findings and Conclusion

The findings show that while training exists, the infrastructure (computerized databases and labs) is severely lacking in Nigeria. Participants strongly affirmed that integrating Forensic Intelligence into

Table 2. Knowledge on programs, workshops, and seminars for Forensic Intelligence.

Question Items	SD	D	A	SA
FI involves thorough evaluation	10 (4.83%)	23 (11.11%)	99 (47.83%)	75 (36.23%)
FI as aspect of crime cycle	15 (7.25%)	38 (18.36%)	91 (43.96%)	63 (30.43%)
FI disrupts/prevents crime	35 (16.91%)	53 (25.60%)	72 (34.78%)	47 (22.71%)
Programs are avenues for education	Nil	13 (6.28%)	103 (49.76%)	91 (43.96%)
Agencies encourage participation	30 (14.49%)	55 (26.57%)	80 (38.65%)	42 (20.29%)

Table 3. Existing computerized data of crimes in local policing.

Question Items	SD	D	A	SA
Daily records are discreetly countered	12 (5.80%)	43 (20.77%)	79 (38.16%)	73 (35.27%)
Data is compiled in softcopy	15 (7.25%)	58 (28.02%)	91 (43.96%)	43 (20.77%)
Data mostly computerized	45 (21.73%)	73 (35.27%)	72 (34.78%)	17 (8.21%)
Personnel have required literacy	22 (10.63%)	33 (15.94%)	99 (47.83%)	53 (25.60%)
System permits documenting with computers	43 (20.77%)	91 (43.96%)	58 (28.02%)	15 (7.25%)

local policing would make investigations faster and more reliable, reducing controversial outcomes in the court of law.

5.1. Conclusion

The solution to mitigate crime commitment is at the high demand for forensic related cases of criminal investigation process. Hence, the application of forensic intelligence; therefore, the aim of this study was effectively and efficiently achieved through the concept of forensic intelligence and no doubt this Forensic Intelligence application processes apply to other West African sub-region.

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